

Innovative concepts and technologies for ECOLOGically sustainable NUTRIent management in agriculture aiming to prevent, mitigate and eliminate pollution in soils, water, and air

Newsletter – Issue 4

May 2025

WELCOME

Welcome to the fourth edition of the [Econutri](#) Newsletter! Within these pages, you will find news and updates on our activities. We invite you to subscribe and explore our website! Follow us on social media and learn more about the world of [Econutri](#).

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Stand-Out Accomplishments

Demonstration Sites

A core pillar of the [Econutri](#) project is its **network of demonstration sites** established across Europe and China. These pilot sites serve as real-world testing grounds for nature-based solutions aimed at improving nutrient use efficiency, reducing environmental pollution, and enhancing agricultural sustainability.

Each site is tailored to local crop types, climate, and agronomic practices, enabling partners to validate and showcase innovations under practical farming conditions. **The overall goal?** To drive down nutrient losses and emissions across animal & plant systems, in order to benefit both the environment and farm productivity.

[Econutri's](#) demonstration sites include:

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📍 Site & Location	🌱 / 🐷 Core Theme
<u>James Hutton Institute</u> Balruddery Farm · Dundee (UK)	🌱 Legume-based regenerative arable cropping (reduced tillage, organic amendments, mixed legumes)
<u>ILVO “Pig Campus”</u> Merelbeke-Melle (BE)	🐷 Real-time barn emissions monitoring
<u>Wonderplant / AUA</u> Drama & Athens (GR)	💧 Closed-loop hydroponics, waste-free fertigation by adjusting nutrients in real time
<u>Vervaet Demos</u> Assenede (BE) & Rusthoeve(NL)	🗑️ Precision manure application
<u>INHORT</u> Skierniewice & Dąbrowice (PL)	🧪 Microbial consortia for compost acceleration & biochar-based “microbial biofertilizers”
<u>Leibniz-ATB</u> Brandenburg (DE)	🐄 Barn additives & management to cut GHG (N ₂ O, CH ₄) and NH ₃ in dairy housing (sensor-feedback control)
<u>CAU</u> Beijing & Nanjing (CN)	🌿 Greenhouse & field inhibitors
<u>SVG</u> Shandong (CN)	🍅 Novel humic-acid & biostimulant fertilizers in greenhouses to slash N/P leaching, NH ₃ & GHG emissions

24 Innovative Technologies Driving Agro-Transformation

At the heart of **Econutri** are **24 cutting-edge technologies** that will be developed and tested across our demo sites. These include:

- Advanced sensors and digital tools for real-time monitoring of nutrient and water levels
- Biostimulants and nano-fertilisers that enhance nutrient uptake
- Water recycling and treatment solutions to reduce input use and environmental risks
- Decision Support Systems (DSS) to guide farmers in precision fertigation and climate-smart practices.

These **scalable, farmer-friendly, and ecologically sound innovations** form a technology portfolio that supports **Econutri's** mission of sustainable nutrient and water use in agriculture. Their allocation across the Work Packages is illustrated below.

A comprehensive overview of the 24 Innovative technologies and each partner's contribution can be found [here](#).

1st eDelphi Survey Results

ESSRG recruited industry and academic experts to understand the concept of nature-based solutions (NBS) and agricultural innovations through best practices. Their verdict?

Participants pointed first to water-centered NBS, especially closed hydroponic circuits, as the standout tools for cutting pollution loads. More details in the full report [here](#).

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Econutri in the spotlight

Inspiring the Next Generation

Between November 2024 and May 2025, **Econutri** partners took their work straight to classrooms and brought classrooms into their fields and greenhouses to inspire students across Europe. These visits sparked curiosity about nature-based nutrient solutions and showed future agronomists, scientists and innovators how sustainable farming can reduce waste and emissions. Highlights are listed below.

4 November 2024 – **ARI** is Introducing Hydroponic Technology to Cyprus' Young Farmers.

25 November 2024 – **ARI** visited Konstantinoupoleos High School in Nicosia and introduced the **Econutri** Project.

4 December 2024 – **UTH** welcomes 1st Vocational High School of Velestino.

5 December 2024 – **NIBIO** visits Secondary school in Sandnes, Norway.

17 January 2025, **ILVO** hosted 6th grade high school students from OLVC Zottegem.

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13 March 2025 – UAL and COEXHAL visit the Nueva Andalucia school in Almeria.

17 March 2025 – ARI welcomes Vocational Students from Crete.

21 April 2025 – COEXPHAL and UAL welcome students from Universidad Autónoma de Chapingo, Spain.

5 May 2025 – UTH welcomes an Upper Secondary School of Thessaloniki to their Greenhouse Facilities.

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Growing Impact: EU–China Journey continues

The EU–China partnership keeps flourishing—between November 2024 and May 2025 it has added new collaborative experiments, intensified knowledge exchange, and staged several coordinated cross-regional outreach events.

2nd Milestone → From **10–13 February 2025** the **Econutri** consortium organized its **second Joint Stakeholder Conference in Almeria**, the heart of Europe’s greenhouse facilities. Hosted by the University of Almeria (UAL) with support from COEXPHAL, Wageningen University & Research (WUR) and China Agricultural University (CAU), the four-day forum focused on **“Optimising Fertigation for Soil–Grown Greenhouse Vegetables.”**

Full details of every activity can be found in the [“News”](#) section of the **Econutri** website (November 2024 to May 2025). A few highlights are summarized below.

- 13 December 2024 – Joint Workshop:** Innovative Solutions for Sustainable Agriculture with UTAD, UNITO, NIBIO and HAAS (HEILONGJIANG) [Read more](#)

- 10–13 February 2025 – 2nd Stakeholder Conference** on Optimizing Fertigation Management of soil-grown crops in Greenhouse Vegetable Production. More details [here](#) and [there](#).

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- 3. **21 April 2025** – Chinese Delegation Explores Agricultural Innovation at UAL. More details [here](#)

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- 4. **10 May 2025** – CAU and InHort organized a Stakeholder Meeting in Kunming, China. [Read more](#)

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Future Events

- 1. [GreenSys2025](#): International Symposium on Advanced Technologies and Management for Sustainable Greenhouse Systems, from 22 to 27 June 2025 in Almeria, Spain.

2. [30th European Society for Rural Sociology Congress](#), with theme: *Navigating rural transitions: Exploring liveable futures*, from 7 to 11 July, 2025, in Riga, Latvia.
3. [Summer School 2025 at AUA](#), on *Sustainable Nutrient Management in Soilless Culture to Optimise Crop Performance and Minimise Environmental Impacts*, hosted by the Agricultural University of Athens (AUA) from 14 to 18 July 2025.
4. [Uiendag/Aardappel Event \(Onion and Potato Day\)](#) on 21 August 2025.
5. [VII EUROSIL 2025](#), Sevilla, Spain from 8 to 12 September 2025
6. [42nd IASP World Conference](#), Beijing, China from 16 to 19 September 2025
7. [19th international RAMIRAN conference](#). Wageningen, Netherlands, from 15 to 17 October 2025

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